

In memoriam Peder Mortensen Personal Memories

Hans Georg K. Gebel

I visited Peder Mortensen in Moesgaard near Aarhus for the first time in 1978 ‘to learn lithics’. Our relationship never really became professional over the decades but remained personal and amicable, even if there were longer breaks in contact, especially during his time in Damascus. I can’t say precisely what connected us. I guess it was because our two hearts equally were and remained turned East – despite a critical distance to many phenomena and events in the countries we loved. I feel the need to write down these memories.

Through Hans Nissen’s mediation and because of my need for training in chipped lithic technologies and analysis, I was able to visit Peder in Moesgaard several times at the end of the 1970s, where he was the museum director at the time. I was accommodated in a guest flat of the Moesgaard manor house and enjoyed his undivided and personal teaching of chipped stone technologies and flint reading. We used his material from Beidha and the Zagros and mine from the “Neolithic” shell middens of Ras al-Hamra near Muscat. These visits brought us closer on a human level: in Peder, I honoured both the patient teacher and the seemingly soft-acting superior. He didn’t freak out when I, an annoying novice in flint technologies, insisted that the intention of the knapper can and must be recognised by the chipped artefact. And I loved his quirky and waggish habits, for example, the behaviour with his favourite ‘browned’ mug and spoon, which he used several times a day to prepare his Nescafé on the windowsill with a great view of the greenery. The friendship between Hans Nissen and Peder Mortensen, fuelled by their field research times in the Zagros, naturally also benefited their academic offspring: This amicable way of caring for the next generation became a role model for me throughout my life. I still want to uphold it today and don’t want to admit that conditions and, thus, the students’ mentalities are changing.

In 1986, Peder received a highly emotional reaction from Diana Kirkbride when he proposed that I assist her in making the final reports on Beidha. Despite Diana Kirkbride kindly supporting my initial steps in the Neolithic of the Greater Petra-Area, she refused to work with a German: Her drastic reaction to Peder’s proposal in his Moesgaard office related to her wartime trauma which she shared with her Danish husband Hans Helbæk who was in the Danish

resistance against the German occupants during the years 1942-1943.

Also unforgettable are the days in 1989 with Peder in one of the Basta workrooms in the Seminar for Ancient Near Eastern Studies at the Berlin Free University, where I explained to him my analysis and recording system for Basta’s chipped stones industry with the material. There seemed to have been some irritation about my ‘measurementalistic’ approach in my study, which led to almost unmanageable amounts of data and appeared monstrous at that time for ‘non-lithic prehistorians’. Peder advised reducing the sample sizes, but this would have meant a resolution problem for more detailed questions about Basta’s lithic economy.

Fig. 1 Young Peder Mortensen published by Tehran Times on December 14, 2022: The article’s title was: “Danish archaeologist Peder Mortensen, famed for Iranian studies, dies at 88.” (Photo: authorship not mentioned in the article)

Peder and his wife’s Inge visit to Basta in 1992 and their participation in the *Central Settlements in Neolithic Jordan* Symposium in Wadi Musa in July 1997 are also unforgettable.

The joint seminars organised by the Carsten Niebuhr Institute at the University of Copenhagen and the Berlin Institute for Ancient Near Eastern Studies from the early 2000s provided an opportunity to meet Peder again more frequently after his return from

Damascus. Peder’s humble and well-hidden waggish-mischievous criticism of student contributions in the seminars was feared among the Danish students. The jovial and seemingly eye-to-eye relationship between the Danish students and their professors concealed a genuine sense of hierarchy and elitism that non-Danes mostly couldn’t figure out. On closer consideration, there were apparent differences in social behaviour in our discipline between the Danes and the Germans, which made these seminars (and our joint work on excavations, e.g., Basta and Ba`ja) exciting and enjoyable also regarding social experience.

Fig. 2 Peder Mortensen chairing sessions at the *Basta Final Symposium* 2008 at Berlin Free University. (Photo: H.G.K. Gebel)

In preparation for the *Basta Final Symposium* 2008, I consulted Peder Mortensen and Bo Dahl Hermansen as ‘kindred spirits’ for the symposium concept. I will never forget how Peder – obviously prepared with all his roguishness – invited us for lunch in his Copenhagen University office. He took a plate and a sterile wrapped cookie, apparently a stored promotional gift, out of the drawer, divided it into three parts, and offered it. He seemed to be a master at creating stories that could easily be retold – and was thus a follower of basic oriental skills.

His and Inge’s participation in the 2008 Basta Final Symposium, which Hans Nissen was instrumental in organising, brought some of Peder’s friends together.

My last personal meeting with Peder was in September 2019, when I gave a lecture dedicated to Bo Dahl Hermansen at the Department of Cross-Cultural

and Regional Studies in Copenhagen. Even then, it was noticeable that he was gradually withdrawing, and not just from this, his last place of work; I followed news of his condition from afar.

Fig. 3 Peder Mortensen in a traditional restaurant in Tehran, 2015. (Photo: H.G.K. Gebel)

The news of his death brought back to me many memories and feelings of great gratitude. How would Inge deal with the loss after so many decades of marriage? How did Peder feel when he left the university and had his personal belongings collected? What traces had he left behind in the discipline, and had these been fully understood and appreciated? Hadn’t he walked just one step ahead of me? And, what a rich life he had led in the Orient, to which he remained devoted all his life, living with all his rich memories. عَلَيْكَ اللَّهُ رَحْمَةً

Peder Mortensen was born in Jutland in May 1934. He graduated in 1960 from Aarhus University with a *magister atrium*. From 1961-1968, he was curator at the National Museum of Denmark, and then – from 1982-1996 – director of Moesgaard Museum. From 1996 to 2001, he was director of the Danish Institute in Damascus before becoming an honorary professor (*adjungeret professor*) at the Department of Cross-Cultural and Regional Studies at Copenhagen University. Peder Mortensen died on December 8th, 2022, at the age of 88 years.

In the Islamic Republic of Iran, Peder Mortensen was always remembered by his former colleagues. He was greatly revered by many of today's archaeology students and postdocs who had never met him in person. On the western side, Peder Mortensen was instrumental in re-starting the excavations at Tepe Guran under the direction of Hojjat Darabi, Kermanshah University, and Tobias Richter, Copenhagen University. A few days after his death, the news was published in the Tehran Times, based on a press release by the National Museum of Iran. In the article, his work and excavations in the Central Zagros, especially in the Hulailan region and in several caves and Tepe Guran, were honoured; the numerous exhibits in the Iran Bastan Museum based on his work were mentioned. Jabrael Nokandeh, the museum's director-general, "expressed his condolences to his family and colleagues, and to the archaeology community, and stated that his name and memory remain in the memory of Iran's cultural heritage", wrote the Tehran Times.

Peder Mortensen had been a member of the Royal Danish Academy of Sciences and Letters and of the Academia Europea. He was honoured in 2004 with a festschrift entitled *From handaxe to khan: Essays presented to Peder Mortensen on the occasion of his 70th birthday* (edited by K. von Folsach, H. Thrane and I. Thuesen; Aarhus University Press).

Peder Mortensen's publications show that he was more than just a prehistorian. As a cultural anthropologist, he had a broad interest in researching, supporting, and safeguarding the Middle East's cultural assets and properties; he and his wife, Inge, were highly engaged in this. He was truly an ambassador of oriental cultures in and outside the Middle East.

In the following, I remember his most outstanding contributions to the prehistory and cultures of the Middle East:

P. Mortensen

1970 *Tell Shimshara: The Hassuna period*. Copenhagen: Munksgaard.

T. Cuyler Young Jr., P.E.L. Smith and P. Mortensen, eds.

1983 *The Hilly Flanks and beyond: essays on the prehistory of southwestern Asia presented to Robert J. Braidwood, November 15, 1982*. Studies in Ancient Oriental Civilisations 36. Chicago: Oriental Institute of the University of Chicago.

P. Mortensen, ed.

2005 *Bayt al-'Aqqad. The history and restoration of a house in old Damascus*. Proceedings of the Danish Institute in Damascus 4. Aarhus: Aarhus University Press.

P. Mortensen, I. Thuesen and I. Demant Mortensen
2013 *Mount Nebo, an archaeological survey of the region: the Palaeolithic and the Neolithic periods I*. Proceedings of the Danish Institute in Damascus 8. Aarhus: Aarhus University Press.

P. Mortensen

2014 *Excavations at Tepe Guran. The Neolithic period*. Acta Iranica 55. Leuven: Peeters.

P. Mortensen

2017 *Eyes on a street in Cairo*. Proceedings of the Danish Institute in Damascus 13. Copenhagen: Orbis Publishing.

In addition, Peder Mortensen supported his wife's, Inge Demant Mortensen, publication *The Nomads of Luristan* (1993; Copenhagen: Rhodos International Science and Art Publishers and London/New York: Thames and Hudson), a most outstanding and deeply heritage-respecting publication on Zagros' mobile pastoralists. All these publications reflect the decades' shifts in Danish social anthropology, paths gone by the Mortensen's that expanded the orientations of Klaus Ferdinand, Johannes Nicolaisen and others from the 1970s onwards.

Hans Georg K. Gebel

ex oriente at Berlin Free University
hggebel@zedat.fu-berlin.de